

Beginner in the Classrooms Text Reading and Studying the Quality of Understanding

Gofurjanova Nilufarkhan Kodirjhan kizi¹

¹ Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of Pedagogy, Department of Primary Education, Trainee Teacher

Abstract:

This article analyzes the criteria for evaluating students' reading literacy. In particular, there are PIRLS (International Reading and Comprehension Study) international programs that determine the quality, level and level of education in the world, and they are widely used as a criterion for further improving the quality of education in developed countries. spoken.

Keywords: quality of education, text, understanding, analysis, criterion, test, primary education.

Introduction.

It is known that in the period of changes, the educational system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society.

Keep that in mind taking general education schools and before school special attention is being paid to strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the young generation to acquire comprehensive knowledge.

Also, with the initiatives of the President, students who have graduated from the 9th grade, parents and, according to their own wishes, consciously college, academic high school or themselves education received in schools mandatory determining that they can continue their education to young people created all kinds of amenities.

As a result of such reforms implemented in our country, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, this situation is the impetus for the further increase in the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists. is happening

The satisfaction of this demand, in turn, creates the need to increase the interest in reading and

classes among young people and to increase the attention of teachers to all-round education through modern social innovations.

The experts of the Independent Institute for Monitoring the Formation of Civil Society are the requirements of today's education system taking into account that it is very important for most foreign countries, he studied some best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of the fields of education and science.

Materials.

In particular, PISA (Program for the International Student Assessment of Educational Achievement), which determines the quality, level and level of education in the world, PIRLS (International Study of Reading and Comprehension of the Text), TIMSS (Mathematics and Science Quality Study at School) there are a number of international programs, such as international monitoring), which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries .

More than 50 countries are participating in the PIRLS study. The purpose of this international research is to study the reading and comprehension skills of primary school students in countries with different educational systems, and the factors in the educational system that cause students to achieve different levels of achievement. 'determining specific characteristics and consists of assessment. Of course, such research is of great importance for workers in the field of public education, scientists, methodologists, teachers, parents and public representatives.

TMSS is also widely used in the education system of the world countries. The TMSS program was organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA), and this study examined the quality of education in mathematics and social studies among students in grades 4 and 8. determines the level, attitude to science, interest. It is held once every 4 years. This study, similar to the PIRLS study, conducts additional surveys among students, school administrators, and teachers, and examines barriers to learning in the field of science. doing main factors determines. This while that's it in the country by comparing developed educational standards and educational efficiency with other countries to see enable will give. 2015 year TMSS studies to the results according to the educational system of countries such as USA, Singapore, Hong Kong, Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia, Great Britain have the highest indicators.

Research and methods.

It should be recognized that in these countries, in order to master high technologies, industrialization and achieve high level of development, special attention is paid to mastering specific sciences at a high level, in which students are more than innate talents and abilities. ra constant work on oneself and the number of students in a group or class in teaching specific subjects

No more than 16 people. Such experience is also available in the USA and since 1999, taking into account that one teacher can educate and educate 16 children during a 40-minute lesson, the number of students in groups in educational institutions is set at 16 by the decision of the president.

In general, in our country, there is no participation of such international programs in the evaluation and monitoring of the educational system, or there is no "National program" for evaluating or monitoring the level of knowledge of young students, the quality of mastery of one or another subject by young people in the region and in the field limits the possibility of determining the scope of work to be carried out and carrying out relevant reforms. Also, the level of teaching in primary and general secondary education institutions lags behind the pace of reforms in the near future. causes a shortage .

Results.

Taking this into account, we consider it permissible to make the following suggestions :

Detailed study of Uzbekistan's participation in international education quality assessment programs and its participation in these programs provide;

Creation of a "National program" for evaluating or monitoring the level of knowledge of students based on international experience;

Taking into account the most advanced results of scientific achievements and the publication of literature in English, consider the issue of implementing various foreign programs that teach English in schools;

To determine the qualification requirements of specialists responsible for education in pre-school educational institutions through specific criteria and to determine by law the full responsibility for the general education of children;

Before school education and common medium education in institutions group and determine the maximum and minimum indicators of the number of students in classes based on methods tested in international experience;

Establishing specialized classes for 8-9-year-olds in every school, separating gifted children from primary classes with the help of psychological tests .

Citizenship society formation monitoring to do independent the head of the branch of the institute Kholmakhmatov Azim Hazratkulovich.

Discussion.

PIRLS-2021: the literacy of students in primary grades is researched by an international organization.

Uzbekistan PIRLS-2021 assessment in the system participation is enough. This about

"Khabar.uz" was informed by the press service of the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers.

Ulugbek Tashkenbayev, Head of the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers, and Andrea Netton, Director of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in Amsterdam, PIRLS of Uzbekistan - The first official meeting was organized on January 25 regarding participation in the 2021 evaluation system.

Remember let's go Uzbekistan Republic Ministers Court An agreement was reached on participation in international assessment studies, including the PISA-2021 international assessment study with the OECD organization, by the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education.

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries. This type of test is designed to be conducted every 5 years, and according to the results of its latest research in 2016, the Russian Federation is leading.

The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement is an international partnership of national research institutes, research agencies, scholars, and analysts working to evaluate, understand, and improve education worldwide. More than 60 countries and more than 100 educational institutions participate in this network of non-profit and independent organizations. Since 1958, the IEA has distinguished itself from other international organizations by creating measures and acceptable recommendations to eliminate deficiencies in the educational system in the process of assessing students' literacy in mathematics, natural sciences, and reading potential.

Conclusion.

to PIRLS preparation

Today each a science the teacher is international assessment has information about the system to be and PISA students and preparation for PIRLS assessment exams is an important task. What is PISA? This is to determine the level of literacy of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences.

PIRLS is an assessment of the level of reading and comprehension of the 4th grade students. TIMSS is an assessment of math and science literacy for 4th and 8th grade students. As a primary education teacher, I connected to the website www.tdi.uz and the channel t.me/milliymarkaz in order to learn more about PIRLS, the international assessment system for 4th graders . We teach students to read and understand the text from the 1st grade. them international assessment level determiner to PIRLS how it is natural to ask the question that it is necessary to prepare. I have started some work in this direction according to the plan. In the reading lessons, I took small stories and fairy tales from the Internet and gave them as homework to the students in 2 different versions. The next day I had a Q&A about the story. "What is the story about?", "Who are the characters?", "What did you learn from the story?", "Which character did you like?" I tested them with questions like

PEARLS TESTS (criterion based on myself made up questions):

"The Punishment of a Bad Horseman" (Abdullah Avloni). "A man had a son named Kasim. He did all sorts of bad things without obeying his father and mother. The children used to fight, fight and tear their clothes. At home, when he was eating the food that his mother had saved for the guest, his mother said: "Kasim, my son! "Did you eat the food?", he would say, "I didn't eat it, the cat ate it." Gradually, he began to steal his father's money. When his father found out, he said, "Son, who took the money?" When he said, "My mother must have taken it," he used to make his mother a thief. One day, his father put a coin on the table and went to sleep. Kasim came and slowly took the coin and put it in his mouth. At that time, when his father tried to catch it, he swallowed the coin. The coin got stuck in Kasim's throat and he died.

children, did you see, bad evil own to begin with enough.

1. The story who about?
A) A child b) Kasim D) Food E) Evil
2. You lie did you speak
A) Yes B) No D) sometimesE) One or two times
3. Kasim to his father the food what ate said ?
A) Cat b) Dog D) Himself E) He didn't say anything
4. Kasim what win sent?
A) The money B) Coin D) Bread E) Food

Through text-based test questions, the student's level of understanding of the text and thinking and reading skills are evaluated.

Used books:

1. Sylvie LaRoche, Mark Joncas. Sample Design in PEARLS, 2016
2. Enemy Pie, Reading for literary experience. Sample PEARLS Passages, Questions, and Scoring Guides, 2016
3. Mahmoud Kashghari." Devonu dictionary - turkish

4. "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", State Scientific Publishing House. Tashkent, 5th floor.
5. "Uzbek of the language explanatory dictionary" 2nd roof 1st floor
6. Kasimova K, Matchonov et al., "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" T "Noshir" 2009.